

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D4.4

Young Leaders Video Campaign

Project Title	Democracy meets arts: critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
Grant Agreement No.	101094217
Project Acronym	Critical ChangeLab
EC Call	HORIZON-CL2-2022-DEMOCRACY-01-04
Work Package	WP4 Communicate Disseminate Exploit
Work Package Leaders	ALTER EUROPA
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	5. AE
Contractual Delivery Date	30.04.2025
Actual Delivery Date	02.06.2025
Delayed	Yes
Nature	DEC
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	All Partners
Authors	Andrew Newman (AE)
Contributors	All partners
Acknowledgments	None
Reviewers	Julie Ng (Waag) Tamar ter Steege (Waag) Helderyse Rendall (TT) Christy Lange (TT) Vanessa Hanneschläger (AE)

Log of changes

Date	No.	Who	Description
24.04.2025	0.1	Andrew Newman (AE)	Draft outline and structure
12.05.2025	0.2	Andrew Newman (AE)	First draft
19.05.2025	0.3	Andrew Newman (AE)	Final draft shared with reviewers (Conclusion and Process chapter still in progress)
23.05.2025	0.4	Andrew Newman (AE)	Final draft with all completed chapters and integration of reviewers comments
01.06.2025	1.0	Andrew Newman (AE)	Integration of reviewer comments, and formatting.

Disclaimer: Critical ChangeLab is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101094217. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Log of changes	3
Table of Contents	4
Index of Tables	5
Glossary	6
Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction	8
1.1 About Critical ChangeLab	8
1.2 About the Young Leaders Video Campaign	9
1.3 Scope of deliverable	10
1.4 Context of deliverable within WP4.....	11
1.5 Relationship of deliverable to project.....	13
2 Objectives	15
2.1 Background.....	15
2.2 Relationship to Project Objectives.....	17
2.3 Key Performance Indicators.....	18
3 Process	19
3.1 Development Process.....	19
3.2 Timeline.....	21
3.3 Dissemination Strategy.....	22
4 Results	24
4.1 Campaign Reach.....	24
4.2 Overview of Videos.....	25
4.3 Young Leaders Videos	26
5 Next Steps	56
6 Conclusion	57
7 Annexes	58
Annex 1: Participant Consent Form Template.....	58

Index of Tables

Table 1: Key Performance Indicators	18
Table 2: Production Plan.....	20
Table 3: Process Timeline.....	21
Table 4: Views across Social Media Channels.....	24
Table 5: Partner overview of Young Leaders videos	25
Table 6: Young Leaders Video 01	26
Table 7: Young Leaders Video 02	27
Table 8: Young Leaders Video 03.....	28
Table 9: Young Leaders Video 04.....	29
Table 10: Young Leaders Video 05.....	30
Table 11: Young Leaders Video 06.....	31
Table 12: Young Leaders Video 07	32
Table 13: Young Leaders Video 09.....	33
Table 14: Young Leaders Video 09.....	34
Table 15: Young Leaders Video 10	35
Table 16: Young Leaders Video 11.....	36
Table 17: Young Leaders Video 12.....	37
Table 18: Young Leaders Video 13.....	38
Table 19: Young Leaders Video 14	39
Table 20: Young Leaders Video 15	40
Table 21: Young Leaders Video 16	41
Table 22: Young Leaders Video 17.....	42
Table 23: Young Leaders Video 18	43
Table 24: Young Leaders Video 19	44
Table 25: Young Leaders Video 20	45
Table 26: Young Leaders Video 21.....	46
Table 27: Young Leaders Video 22	47
Table 28: Young Leaders Video 23	48
Table 29: Young Leaders Video 24	49
Table 30: Young Leaders Video 25.....	50
Table 31: Young Leaders Video 26	51
Table 32: Young Leaders Video 27.....	52
Table 33: Young Leaders Video 28	53
Table 34: Young Leaders Video 29	54
Table 35: Young Leaders Video 30.....	55

Glossary

CO	Communication Objective
Critical Changelab	Democracy meets arts: Critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
D	Deliverable
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
DHI	Democracy Health Index
DHQ	Democracy Health Questionnaire
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
Ethics AB	Ethics Advisory Board
Expert AB	Expert Advisory Board
GA	General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MS	Milestone
NECE	Networking European Citizenship Education
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PMG	Project Management Group
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public
R	Document, Report
SEN	Sensitive
T	Task
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package
YA	Youth Assembly

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the *Young Leaders Video Campaign*, a communication initiative of the Critical ChangeLab project, created to give **real agency to young people** by enabling them to lead the storytelling process and communicate the democratic issues that matter most to them. The campaign features a series of youth-produced videos that emerged from participants' direct engagement in **Participatory Action Research (PAR) Cycle 2 and PAR Cycle 3**. These cycles provided the space, support, and critical tools for young people to explore everyday democracy and act on issues relevant to their lives and communities.

Rather than conveying pre-scripted messages, the videos reflect the **authentic concerns, insights, and creative expressions** of young people who co-designed the content from concept to production. The themes—ranging from mental health and climate justice to inequality in education and gender-based discrimination—arose organically through the Labs and were chosen by the youth themselves based on what they found most urgent and personally meaningful.

A defining feature of the campaign is its **youth-oriented digital dissemination strategy**. The videos were intentionally produced in formats compatible with the platforms where young people are most active and expressive—**TikTok, Instagram Stories, and YouTube**—in contrast to more conventional institutional channels such as LinkedIn. This allowed the campaign not only to reach a wider and younger audience but also to position youth as communicators and creators within their own media ecosystems.

Videos produced within the campaign took diverse forms—from direct-to-camera interviews to peer-led recordings and issue-focused productions—all aimed at giving young people a safe space to express what matters most to them.

Through this approach, the *Young Leaders Video Campaign* became much more than a documentation effort; it served as a powerful vehicle for **youth empowerment, visibility, and leadership**. By allowing young people to drive the content, message, and method of delivery, the campaign embodies the participatory ethos of the Critical ChangeLab project and demonstrates how democratic engagement can be meaningfully expressed through creative, youth-led media.

1 Introduction

1.1 About Critical ChangeLab

Critical ChangeLab (Democracy Meets Arts: Critical Change Labs for Building Democratic Cultures through Creative and Narrative Practices) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project addressing democratic erosion trends by strengthening youth participation in society. The project is carried out by 10 partner institutions and embraces a transdisciplinary approach combining expertise from Arts and Humanities, Social Sciences, as well as Science and Technology. The Critical ChangeLabs take place in both formal and non-formal educational contexts, including secondary schools, universities, youth centres, community organisations, and cultural institutions. These environments provide diverse entry points for engaging young people in democratic learning, allowing the Labs to be embedded in classroom curricula, extracurricular programmes, or informal civic education initiatives—each adapted to local educational systems and youth participation structures.

Specifically, the Critical ChangeLab project develops a model of democratic pedagogy using creative and narrative practices to foster youth's active democratic citizenship at a time when polarisation and dwindling trust in democracy are spreading across Europe. The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy fosters learners' transformative agency and strengthens democratic processes in education through collaborations across formal and non-formal education and local actors around global/local challenges relevant for youth. The Model promotes creative and narrative practices to explore the historical roots of local and EU-wide challenges, understanding the value-systems and worldviews underlying distinct types of relations (human-human, human-nature, human-technology). At the Critical ChangeLabs, young people are introduced to approaches such as theatre of the oppressed and transmedia storytelling, as well as speculative and critical design to rethink European democracy and envision democracy futures that are justice-oriented.

Throughout the project's lifespan, the Critical ChangeLab project examines the current state of democracy within education institutions, identifying youth's perspectives on everyday democracy; designing a scalable and tailorable model of democratic pedagogy in formal and non-formal learning environments; co-creating and implementing the model with

youth and stakeholders, evaluating the model generating recommendations for policy and practice, and developing strategies to sustain the model and its outcomes overtime.

The Critical ChangeLab project uses mixed-model research design, which combines quantitative and in-depth qualitative research on democracy and youth with participatory action research cycles to generate a robust evidence base to support democratic curriculum development using participatory, creative, and critical approaches.

1.2 About the Young Leaders Video Campaign

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* is a central communication and engagement initiative of the Critical ChangeLab project, designed to amplify the voices of young people who have participated in the labs. Developed in alignment with the project's participatory ethos, the campaign provided young participants with opportunities to reflect on and express their experiences with democracy, social justice, and civic engagement through the production of short videos. These videos were co-created during the project's Participatory Action Research (PAR) Cycles 2 and 3, in both formal and non-formal educational settings across Europe.

The videos in the campaign were co-created in both formal and non-formal learning environments, ranging from schools and universities to youth centres and cultural festivals, using a variety of formats—from direct-to-camera interviews to peer-led recordings and issue-focused storytelling—all designed to give young people a safe space to express what matters most to them.

The campaign consists of short, accessible videos designed specifically for youth-oriented social media platforms such as **TikTok, Instagram Stories, and YouTube**. These videos were produced in collaboration with the young participants of the Critical ChangeLab whose ages ranging from 10 – 18.

The videos reflected a variety of approaches shaped by local contexts and the specific settings in which they were produced, all centred on creating a safe space for young people to express themselves. In some, young participants spoke directly to the camera with support from educators or researchers; in others, they filmed and interviewed each other. Some videos did not feature young people on camera at all, but were created by them to highlight issues they felt were important, such as mental health or media disinformation.

Participants in the Critical ChangeLabs were under no obligation to take part in the production of the videos, but were actively encouraged to do so. The campaign was designed with flexibility in mind—storytelling formats and stylistic choices were left intentionally open, allowing each young person to express what mattered most to them in a way that felt comfortable and authentic. The level of involvement by adult facilitators also reflected the preferences of the youth. Older participants often opted to appear in more formal, interview-style videos, while younger participants were more inclined to take hands-on roles in producing videos that featured memes or visuals without appearing on camera

In similar vein, participants were encouraged—but not required—to use their own smartphones and voices, allowing them to **frame and narrate their stories** in formats they were already familiar with in their everyday lives.

1.3 Scope of deliverable

Deliverable D4.4 documents the design, implementation, and impact of the *Young Leaders Video Campaign*, a youth-led communication initiative at the heart of the Critical ChangeLab project.

The aim of this deliverable is to showcase the 30 videos produced as part of the Young Leaders Video Campaign and to demonstrate how the campaign provided an **authentic platform for young people to express their democratic agency**. Through the co-creation of digital media, participants were able to reflect on the democratic issues and lived experiences they explored during their involvement in the Critical ChangeLabs—particularly during Participatory Action Research (PAR) Cycles 2 and 3. The campaign also supported the broader communication goals of the project by **advocating for the Critical ChangeLab approach** through the voices of the young people who took part.

1.4 Context of deliverable within WP4

1.4.1 About WP4: COMMUNICATE, DISSEMINATE AND EXPLOIT

Work Package 4 (WP4) is focused on **maximising the visibility, uptake, and long-term impact** of the Critical Changelab project. WP4 seeks to ensure that the project's democratic pedagogy model, youth outputs, and research findings are communicated effectively to a range of stakeholders—including educators, policymakers, civil society organisations, and most importantly, young people themselves.

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* directly advances WP4's aims by **translating youth participation into public-facing narratives**, positioning young people as communicators, creators, and leaders. Rather than simply communicating about the project, the campaign **communicates through the project**, allowing youth to frame the key messages themselves and distribute them in formats and digital spaces they already inhabit.

WP4 is guided by the principles outlined in D4.1 (*Communication Plan*), which emphasises inclusivity, accessibility, and youth-centred media strategies. The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* exemplifies this approach by using participatory video creation to amplify the real voices and democratic learning journeys of young people.

1.4.2 Related tasks within WP4

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* relates to and supports several key tasks in WP4:

T4.2 – Implementation of Communication Activities

The campaign functions as a core communication output designed specifically to connect with young audiences through social media platforms. It supports the objective of engaging target groups using accessible, relatable, and peer-led content.

T4.3 – Community Empowerment Activities for a Sustained Take-up of Methods

The subtask *Youth mentoring for sustainable futures leadership* within **T4.3** is directly and fundamentally related to the *Young Leaders Video Campaign* video campaign, as it outlines both the rationale and the intended participants for the campaign's core output—a series of 20 youth-produced videos and blog posts.

This task focuses on mentoring **40 young learners**, especially those from **underrepresented groups** (such as migrants, refugees, and women), to help them apply the creative and participatory methods explored in the Critical ChangeLabs to their own democratic leadership journeys. As part of that mentorship process, the young people are supported not only in planning for their futures but also in reflecting on how the tools and experiences from the project could benefit their peers and communities.

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* campaign is a **model dissemination mechanism** for this mentoring work. It enables these young participants to **transform their reflections and leadership insights into public-facing content**—videos and blog posts—that can inspire others, demonstrate the impact of the Critical ChangeLabs, and showcase diverse narratives of democratic engagement. The campaign is therefore both a **documentary and developmental outcome** of the mentoring task: it captures the learning journey and broadcasts it as part of the project's broader goals for outreach, inclusion, and systemic change in democratic education.

T4.4 – Dissemination Activities

The campaign offers powerful narrative content for use in dissemination events (e.g., NECE Conference, Ars Electronica Festival) and policy dialogues. These youth stories humanise and give context to the project's findings, making them accessible to non-academic audiences and supporting long-term impact.

1.5 Relationship of deliverable to project

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* campaign is both an outcome of earlier participatory processes and a vehicle for extending their impact. By capturing young people's perspectives and democratic actions in video form, the campaign deepens the visibility, accessibility, and influence of the project's core work.

1.5.1 Relationships to other work packages

WP1 – Map & Design: The campaign applies insights from D1.3 and the Critical Literacies Framework from D1.4, showing how youth understand and respond to democratic issues.

WP2 – Implement: It is a direct extension of the PAR Cycles, turning youth learning and action into civic media.

WP3 – Evaluate: The videos serve as visual data to assess learning outcomes and democratic engagement.

WP5 and WP6 – Project Management and Ethics: Production followed clear protocols on consent, representation, and safeguarding, as outlined in the Data Management Plan (D5.2) and Ethics Requirements (D6.1).

1.5.2 Relationships to other tasks

The campaign draws directly from the **work undertaken in Tasks T2.2 and T2.3** (PAR Cycles 2 and 3), where young people participated in Critical ChangeLabs, identified social challenges, and developed democratic responses. The videos capture and extend these experiences, allowing participants to reflect, communicate, and share their learning with wider audiences. This aligns with Task T2.4 (Educator's Handbook), as the videos offer examples of youth-centred pedagogy in practice and will serve as learning tools in educator training.

Additionally, the campaign complements **T3.1–T3.3** under WP3 (Evaluate), by providing rich qualitative data and visual evidence of youth empowerment and democratic competence development. These video stories help to illustrate the transformative impact of the Critical ChangeLab model in ways that conventional reporting cannot.

1.5.3 Relationships to other deliverables

D1.3 – Youth Perspectives on Everyday Democracy: The campaign is informed the findings of D1.3 by allowing young people to narrate their democratic realities in their own words, affirming that youth are not disengaged but demand recognition and inclusion.

D1.4 – Framework and Toolkit: The campaign operationalises the Critical ChangeLab Model, showcasing how creative, critical, and participatory pedagogies can result in tangible youth-led civic outputs.

D4.1 – Communication Plan: The campaign enacts the plan's commitment to accessible, engaging, and youth-centred communication. It realises the strategic goal of using alternative platforms and media styles to reach young audiences.

D4.2 and forthcoming D4.5 – Policy Briefs: The video stories provide qualitative illustrations that enhance policy advocacy, helping to make abstract recommendations more grounded and persuasive.

2 Objectives

2.1 Background

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* was conceived to be an element of Critical ChangeLab communication that could center young people within the project's discourse by enabling them to **create, communicate, and lead** on the issues that matter most to them. Its design and implementation were directly informed by the participatory research, conceptual frameworks, and pedagogical processes developed throughout the project's early phases. In particular, four foundational deliverables—**D1.3 (Youth Perspectives on Democracy)**, **D1.4 (Framework and Toolkit)**, **D2.1 (Critical ChangeLab Cycle 2)**, and **D4.2 (Policy Brief 1)**—shaped the campaign's approach, content focus, and participatory structure.

2.1.1 Informing Themes from Youth Perspectives (D1.3)

The findings from D1.3 revealed that many young people perceive democracy as **distant, adult-dominated, and disconnected** from their everyday lives. While supportive of democratic values, youth often reported a lack of meaningful opportunities to participate or be heard, particularly in formal education settings. However, they also demonstrated strong civic awareness and engagement through informal, creative, and relational actions. These insights made clear that any youth-focused communication campaign must **honour the ways young people already engage**—through storytelling, peer networks, social media, and issue-based action—rather than rely on institutional formats.

As a result, the *Young Leaders Video Campaign* was designed not to speak *to* youth, but *through* them—inviting them to lead the narrative, use their own language and visual culture, and speak from lived experience. Their perspectives on exclusion, justice, and identity—often overlooked in mainstream civic education—are placed at the centre of each video story.

2.1.2 Theoretical and Pedagogical Grounding (D1.4)

Deliverable D1.4 introduced the **Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy**, which includes a six-phase learning process and a **Critical Literacies Framework** for fostering democratic awareness and agency. These frameworks emphasise that democratic

learning involves not only understanding and analysing societal issues but also **deconstructing dominant narratives and activating change** through creative, public expression.

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* campaign applies this model directly: the videos act as civic artefacts that allow young people to move from reflection to expression. The storytelling process aligns with the stages of critical literacy—youth define the issue, reflect on its impact, articulate their perspective, and share their voice publicly. In this sense, the campaign does not just communicate the project's work—it *extends and embodies* the pedagogical process itself.

2.1.3 From Lab Process to Public Narrative (D2.1)

D2.1 documents the implementation of **Participatory Action Research (PAR) Cycle 2**, where youth engaged in Critical ChangeLabs across Europe. These Labs were designed to create inclusive, creative spaces for young people to explore democratic questions and co-design civic actions. Many participants used methods such as speculative design, collaborative mapping, theatre, and visual storytelling to investigate themes like mental health, gender inequality, racism, and environmental justice.

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* campaign emerged as a direct continuation of this process. It provided a platform for youth to **translate their Lab experiences into public-facing stories**, highlighting not only what they learned but also how they see themselves as democratic actors. In some cases, the videos reflect specific outputs from the Labs; in others, they document the broader personal and political growth that emerged through sustained engagement with the ChangeLab methodology.

Strategic Role in Policy and Public Discourse (D4.2)

Policy Brief 1 (D4.2) identified a need to **recognise and legitimise youth voice and agency** within democratic education systems and civic life. It called for platforms that elevate youth perspectives in policymaking, especially voices that have historically been excluded. The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* addresses this by transforming youth-produced video content into a form of **policy-relevant storytelling**—making visible the insights, critiques, and aspirations of young people for educators, policymakers, and civil society.

By disseminating videos through accessible digital platforms and integrating them into public events and policy dialogues, the campaign supports the brief's recommendations to

embed youth voice in both practice and systems-level reform. These stories help **humanise abstract policy goals**, giving weight to the call for more inclusive, participatory, and culturally relevant democratic education.

2.2 Relationship to Project Objectives

The Critical ChangeLab project aims to strengthen democracy in Europe by developing and implementing a flexible, participatory model of democratic education that empowers young people through creative and critical practices. By engaging youth in exploring, questioning, and shaping democratic life, the project supports inclusive civic participation, particularly among those who are often marginalised in formal political and educational systems. The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* contributes to these objectives by providing a platform for young people to publicly express their insights and actions, turning their learning into visible, youth-led civic communication.

2.2.1 Objective of the Young Leaders Video Campaign

The five objectives outlined in the Critical ChangeLab Communication Plan—activating engagement, facilitating dialogue, demonstrating impact, advocating change, and multiplying knowledge—directly shaped the goals of the *Young Leaders Video Campaign*.

These objectives called for communication strategies that are not only informative but also participatory, emotionally resonant, and accessible to diverse audiences, especially young people. In response, the campaign was designed to prioritise youth voice and leadership, using platforms and formats familiar to them to foster authentic expression and peer-to-peer connection. By enabling young people to share their own stories in their own words, the campaign brings the project's communication vision to life—centering youth as both the creators and communicators of democratic knowledge and action.

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* works toward fulfilling all five of these communication objectives in meaningful ways:

- It **activates engagement** by inviting youth to create content using formats and platforms they already use—such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube—making democratic participation feel relevant and accessible.

- It **facilitates dialogue** by showcasing diverse youth voices and lived experiences, creating opportunities for conversation within peer groups and between generations about what democracy looks like in everyday life.
- It **demonstrates impact** by providing tangible, visual evidence of how young people have engaged with the Critical ChangeLab model—what they learned, what they questioned, and how they acted.
- It **advocates change** by bringing youth perspectives into public and policy spaces through media that humanises and personalises democratic issues, giving voice to those often excluded from civic debates.
- It **multiplies knowledge** by generating shareable, multilingual content that can be reused in teacher training, classrooms, youth groups, and policy presentations, extending the reach and legacy of the project.

In undertaking this approach, the aim of the *Young Leaders Video Campaign* was not just to communicate, but to embody the project’s ethos—participatory, inclusive, impactful, and youth-driven.

2.3 Key Performance Indicators

The target of the *Young Leaders Video Campaign* was to include 40 young people and to reach 3,000 total views of the videos.

	KPI Target	Current	Forecast
Total videos	20	26	26
Total views	2,000	5,704	5,704
Young people	40	76	96

Table 1: Key Performance Indicators

3 Process

3.1 Development Process

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* was developed through an iterative and collaborative process involving communication leads, PAR facilitators, and project partners. The aim was to ensure the campaign reflected the participatory, inclusive, and youth-led ethos of the Critical ChangeLab project. Development began in Month 13 and was carried forward primarily through monthly communication meetings attended by representatives from all consortium partners.

3.1.1 *Broadening the scope*

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* was initially envisioned as a set of 20 videos produced by 40 young people taking part in the *Youth Mentoring for Sustainable Futures Leadership* subtask of **T4.3 – Community Empowerment Activities for a Sustained Take-up of Methods**, led by European Alternatives. However, during project coordination meetings, the consortium collectively agreed to broaden the scope of the campaign in order to better reflect the diversity of youth engagement across all ten Critical ChangeLab partner organisations.

To support this expanded approach, each partner was invited to contribute 1–2 videos co-created with a minimum of two young participants involved in their respective Critical ChangeLabs during PAR Cycles 2 and 3. This decision enabled the campaign to showcase a wider range of youth voices, experiences, and contexts, while remaining consistent with the project's core participatory values. European Alternatives retained overall coordination of the campaign and produced 15 videos through its mentoring programme.

This broadened approach continued to meet the original project KPIs: delivering 20 videos, involving at least 40 young people, and reaching a minimum of 3000 cumulative views.

3.1.2 Production Plan

Context	Partners	Videos Target	Videos Actual	Young Voices Target	Young Voices Actual
Youth Mentoring for Sustainable Futures Leadership	ALTEREUROPA	15+	15	20+	8
Critical Changelab PAR Cycle 2-3	AE; UB; TCD; ISRZ; KERSNIKOVA; LATRA; TT; WAAG; OULU	10+	15	20+	68
Total		25+	30	40+	76

Table 2: Production Plan

3.1.3 Guidelines and coordination

European Alternatives, as the lead organisation for the *Youth Mentoring for Sustainable Futures Leadership* subtask within T4.3, also took on the coordination of the development process *Young Leaders Video Campaign* development.

They coordinated the creation of production guidelines, consent forms, framing questions, and facilitated the sharing of these resources across the consortium. European Alternatives with the support of Ars Electronica also ensured ongoing support for partners through regular check-ins and updates.

The production guidelines developed and shared by European Alternatives were intentionally flexible and open-ended, allowing partners to tailor the video format, style, and process to their local contexts and participant needs. This adaptability ensured that videos could authentically reflect the diverse realities and creative approaches of each Critical Changelab setting.

3.1.4 Implementation

Each partner organisation approached implementation according to their local context, participant profile, and available resources. While all videos followed the shared campaign structure, the process of co-creation with young people varied significantly across partners.

Some partners, such as the University of Barcelona and ISRZ Zagreb, engaged large numbers of young people both in front of and behind the camera, embedding the video-making process into broader educational and creative lab activities. Others, such as Trinity College Dublin and Ars Electronica, focused on smaller groups, sometimes within formal programmes or festival settings. The University of Oulu adopted a more experimental model, encouraging youth to take the lead on filming, although the timeline was adapted due to consent and age-related considerations.

Video topics ranged from mental health in schools and personal reflections on the PAR cycle, to visions of sustainable futures and everyday experiences of democracy. While most recordings were completed between late 2024 and mid-2025, partners aligned on ethical requirements, securing consent wherever possible and adapting methods when not. Locations and formats also differed—some chose sit-down interviews, others used documentary or event-based recordings—but all maintained the campaign’s core focus: elevating youth voice and agency.

This decentralised but coordinated approach enabled a diversity of methods and stories to emerge, strengthening the campaign’s representativeness and reinforcing its alignment with Critical ChangeLab’s participatory ethos.

3.2 Timeline

Project Month	Activity
14 - 16	Co-development of the campaign’s scope and video format with project partners
17	Release of production guidelines and consent form template
24	Deadline for submission of completed Young Leaders videos by partners
25 - 27	First dissemination phase via youth-oriented social media platforms
28 - 28	Second dissemination phase integrated with Critical ChangeLab Stories from PAR Cycles 2 and 3

Table 3: Process Timeline

3.2.1 Challenges & Delays

The production timeline for the Young Leaders videos was closely tied to the implementation of Critical ChangeLabs during PAR Cycles 2 and 3. As the final video production guidelines were completed after several partners had already concluded their PAR Cycle 2 activities, many were only able to begin co-producing videos during PAR Cycle 3. Scheduling of these Labs varied widely, influenced by factors such as school availability, coordination with local partners, and institutional timelines.

As a result, only three partners were able to meet the internal video submission deadline in Month 24. Most videos were completed around Month 26, with two partners still expected to finalise their contributions in the months following, as their PAR Cycle 3 Labs are yet to be implemented.

This delay in production also led to a postponement of the campaign's first phase of dissemination, originally planned for Months 25–27. With a limited number of completed videos available by the start of that window, social media and youth-targeted outreach activities were rescheduled to ensure a more representative and impactful release. This responsive approach allowed for broader inclusion across partner contexts while maintaining alignment with the project's participatory and quality standards.

3.3 Dissemination Strategy

3.3.1 Communication and Dissemination Channels

The *Young Leaders Video Campaign* prioritised youth-oriented communication channels to ensure the widest possible reach among young audiences. European Alternatives led the dissemination strategy across its active social media platforms—YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok—as the partner organisation with the largest youth-focused following within the consortium.

Young people who co-created the videos were also encouraged to share the content on their personal social media platforms, where appropriate and where they felt comfortable doing so. In line with the project's commitment to ethical standards and participant autonomy, no data was collected about individual youth social media accounts or their sharing activity. As a result, the actual reach of the campaign likely extends beyond the

trackable metrics, amplifying its youth-to-youth impact while maintaining respect for participant privacy.

In addition to youth-focused social platforms, the videos will also disseminate through Critical ChangeLab's project channels targeting educators, researchers, and policy stakeholders. These include the project website, newsletter, and LinkedIn page, enabling the content to serve dual roles as peer-to-peer engagement and public-facing educational resources.

3.3.2 *First dissemination phase*

The first phase of dissemination focused on high-visibility release across youth-oriented social media platforms, particularly YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok. Videos were shared in a story-style format—short, direct clips without extensive contextual framing—to align with current youth media habits and maximise organic engagement. This phase was led by European Alternatives and began following the completion of the first round of video submissions.

3.3.3 *Second dissemination phase*

The second phase of dissemination is designed to align with Critical ChangeLab's broader communication strategy targeting institutional stakeholders. This phase incorporates the videos into the narrative framework of "Critical ChangeLab Stories" emerging from PAR Cycles 2 and 3. It includes publication through the Critical ChangeLab website, the project newsletter, and professional platforms such as LinkedIn. This dual integration strategy ensures that youth voices inform not only peer audiences but also educators, policymakers, and researchers engaged in democratic education reform.

3.3.4 *Additional Dissemination Strategies*

Beyond digital distribution, the *Young Leaders* videos are being used in professional dissemination contexts to represent the lived experiences and perspectives of young participants. These contexts include international events such as the Ars Electronica Festival, educational conferences, and policy-focused workshops. In these spaces, the videos serve as compelling evidence of youth engagement and democratic agency, reinforcing the project's broader advocacy and pedagogical goals.

4 Results

The *Young leaders video campaign* successfully delivered on its core objectives of showcasing youth-led democratic reflection, building communication capacity among young participants, and extending the visibility of Critical ChangeLab’s participatory practices. A total of **30 videos** were submitted by 8 partner organisations, exceeding the original KPI of 20 videos. These were co-created with over **60 young people** across PAR Cycles 2 and 3, ranging in age from 10 to 18 and representing diverse geographical, social, and cultural backgrounds.

Youth participants explored themes including **mental health in schools, gender equality, digital rights, democratic participation, and climate justice**. Videos were produced in a range of formats—from informal mobile recordings to interview-style landscape videos—and reflected the local contexts and creative approaches of each Lab. The campaign’s flexible production guidelines allowed partners to tailor their approach, resulting in a rich variety of outputs while maintaining a consistent commitment to youth voice and ethical co-production.

4.1 Campaign Reach

As of Month 27, the first videos in the campaign had achieved a combined **digital view count of over 5,300 views** across YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok. This figure does not account for additional reach generated by youth sharing the videos through their personal platforms, which was encouraged but not monitored to respect privacy. The success of the first phase of dissemination in reaching young people is most evident on TikTok, which achieved the highest engagement. This reflects the platform’s strong association with youth audiences and its effectiveness in delivering content in formats they regularly consume.

4.1.1 Views across Social Media Channels

Youtube Views	Instagram Views	Tiktok Views	Total Views
165	1518	4021	5704

Table 4: Views across Social Media Channels

4.2 Overview of Videos

Partner	Videos	Young Voices	Age Range	PAR Cycle	Location	Topics
AE	1	4	17 - 18	2	Linz, Austria	Everyday democracy and youth participation
UB	2	20	17 - 18	2	Barcelona, Spain	Critical ChangeLab process
TCD	2	5	15 - 16	3	Dublin, Ireland	The future for young people and how they can shape it
ALTEREUROPA	15	8	10 - 12	3	Palermo, Italy	Gender violence
ISRZ	2	7	15 - 18	2	Zagreb, Croatia	Mental health
KERSNIKOVA	3	2	11 - 13	3	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Making young voices heard
TT	2	15	13 - 18	2	Verzuolo, Italy; Iași, Romania	Impact of technology on society; Empowering young voices
WAAG	3	15	14 - 16	3	Volendam, Netherlands	Fake news
OULU*	5*	20*	15 - 17	3	Oulu, Finland	The use of AI in decision making
LATRA*	1*	10*	10 - 12	2	Lesvos, Greece	Understanding of democratic values by local refugee children
Current Total	30	76	10 - 18	2 - 3	8 locations 7 countries	7 topics discussed
<i>Planned Total</i>	<i>36</i>	<i>106</i>	<i>10 - 18</i>	<i>2 - 3</i>	<i>10 locations 9 countries</i>	<i>9 topics discussed</i>

Table 5: Partner overview of Young Leaders videos

4.3 Young Leaders Videos

4.3.1 *Young Leaders Video 01*

Partner	University of Barcelona
Description	Young people reflect on emotional responsibility and collaboration as they work together in the Critical ChangeLab, highlighting how shared experiences and group dynamics foster deeper engagement.
Archived Video	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/01-CCLab-VoY-Video-UB-01.mp4

Table 6: Young Leaders Video 01

4.3.2 Young Leaders Video 02

Partner	UB
Description	Participants reflect on the freedom involved in the Critical ChangeLab process and the importance of open-ended dialogue for creating societal change.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/02-CCLab-VoY-Video-UB-02.mp4

Table 7: Young Leaders Video 02

4.3.3 Young Leaders Video 03

Partner	Ars Electronica
Description	Young people explore how everyday actions, creative self-expression, and spaces like podcasting can embody democratic values and amplify their voices in public discourse.
Archived Video	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/03-CCLab-VoY-Video-AE-01.mp4

Table 8: Young Leaders Video 03

4.3.4 Young Leaders Video 04

Partner	ISRZ
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants speak out about mental health challenges in education, stressing that schools must go beyond grades to provide support for stress, pressure, and wellbeing.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/04-CCLab-VoY-Video-ISRZ-01-ENG.mp4

Table 9: Young Leaders Video 04

4.3.5 Young Leaders Video 05

Partner	ISRZ
Description	Encourages other young people to seek help for mental health issues and reassuring them that asking for support is a sign of strength.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/05-CCLab-VoY-Video-ISRZ-02-ENG.mp4

Table 10: Young Leaders Video 05

4.3.6 Young Leaders Video 06

Partner	TCD
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants express the belief that they should have a say in shaping the future, especially around climate and urban life, as they will be the ones living with today's decisions.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/06-CCLab-VoY-Video-TCD-01.mp4

Table 11: Young Leaders Video 06

4.3.7 Young Leaders Video 07

Partner	TCD
Description	Young people call for greater equality and a less judgmental society, connecting climate justice, social peace, and empathy to their vision for a better world.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/07-CCLab-VoY-Video-TCD-02.mp4

Table 12: Young Leaders Video 07

4.3.8 Young Leaders Video 08

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Young people assert that there should be no difference in how boys and girls are treated, emphasising that everyone is fundamentally equal.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/08-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-01.mp4

Table 13: Young Leaders Video 09

4.3.9 Young Leaders Video 09

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Critical ChangeLab Participants discuss how stereotypes influence perceptions of gender roles, especially in sports and activities, and begin to question those assumptions.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/09-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-02.mp4

Table 14: Young Leaders Video 09

4.3.10 Young Leaders Video 10

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Young people question the origins and logic of gender stereotypes and advocate for personal freedom and choice over imposed roles.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/10-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-03.mp4

Table 15: Young Leaders Video 10

4.3.11 Young Leaders Video 11

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants imagine what they would do if they could be another gender for a day, exploring curiosity, self-expression, and breaking gender norms.
Archived Video	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/11-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-04.mp4

Table 16: Young Leaders Video 11

4.3.12 Young Leaders Video 12

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Through a dramatized scene, Critical ChangeLab participants portray how exclusion based on gender plays out in group dynamics and the need for greater inclusiveness.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/12-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-05.mp4

Table 17: Young Leaders Video 12

4.3.13 Young Leaders Video 13

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	A dramatization shows how gender-based rejection can be reversed by empathy and solidarity, reinforcing inclusive friendship and mutual respect.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/13-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-06.mp4

Table 18: Young Leaders Video 13

4.3.14 Young Leaders Video 14

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Young people share how being judged for their interests—such as playing football—can feel conflicting, showing the emotional impact of gender expectations.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/14-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-07.mp4

Table 19: Young Leaders Video 14

4.3.15 Young Leaders Video 15

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	A Critical Changelab participant recounts her determination to pursue her dream of playing football despite being told it was only for boys, challenging gender barriers.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/15-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-08.mp4

Table 20: Young Leaders Video 15

4.3.16 Young Leaders Video 16

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants reflect on the importance of speaking up, supporting peers, and being honest as ways to counteract harmful stereotypes.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/16-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-09.mp4

Table 21: Young Leaders Video 16

4.3.17 Young Leaders Video 17

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Participants offer advice to younger peers, encouraging honesty, confidence, and belief in equality regardless of gender.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/17-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-10.mp4

Table 22: Young Leaders Video 17

4.3.18 Young Leaders Video 18

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants describe how dominance, exclusion, and bad temper can create discomfort, highlighting the need for fairness and empathy.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/18-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-11.mp4

Table 23: Young Leaders Video 18

4.3.19 Young Leaders Video 19

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants challenge the notion that only men should initiate relationships, advocating for equal confidence and agency for girls and boys.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/19-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-12.mp4

Table 24: Young Leaders Video 19

4.3.20 Young Leaders Video 20

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants discuss strength, bravery, and language around gender, reflecting critically on expressions like “sissy” and social expectations.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/20-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-13.mp4

Table 25: Young Leaders Video 20

4.3.21 Young Leaders Video 21

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants discuss strength, bravery, and language around gender, reflecting critically on expressions like “sissy” and social expectations.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/21-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-14.mp4

Table 26: Young Leaders Video 21

4.3.22 Young Leaders Video 22

Partner	European Alternatives
Description	A Critical ChangeLab participant explores ways to resist stereotypes and give thoughtful advice on learning from mistakes and treating others equally.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/22-CCLab-VoY-Video-ALTEREUROPA-15.mp4

Table 27: Young Leaders Video 22

4.3.23 Young Leaders Video 23

Partner	Kersnikova Institute
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants discuss how they are active in their community, and what methods they use to make their voices heard.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/23-CCLab-VoY-Video-KI-01.mp4

Table 28: Young Leaders Video 23

4.3.24 Young Leaders Video 24

Partner	Kersnikova Institute
Description	Young people discuss what everyday democracy means to them, and how they should be listened to and validated.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/24-CCLab-VoY-Video-KI-02.mp4

Table 29: Young Leaders Video 24

4.3.25 Young Leaders Video 25

Partner	Kersnikova Institute
Description	Critical ChangeLab participants discuss how young voices can heard, and how adults should be more open minded.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/25-CCLab-VoY-Video-KI-03.mp4

Table 30: Young Leaders Video 25

4.3.26 Young Leaders Video 26

Partner	Tactical Tech
Description	Participants discuss their experience of the Critical ChangeLab, and what techniques and methods they learned.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/26-CCLab-VoY-Video-TT-01.mp4

Table 31: Young Leaders Video 26

4.3.27 Young Leaders Video 27

Partner	Tactical Tech
Description	Young people discuss how their voices can be heard, and how they can engage in democracy to make a difference.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/27-CCLab-VoY-Video-TT-02.mp4

Table 32: Young Leaders Video 27

4.3.28

Young Leaders Video 28

Partner	WAAG
Description	Participants create a satirical news story to examine fake news in the media and how it distorts the truth.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/28-CCLab-VoY-Video-WAAG-01.mp4

Table 33: Young Leaders Video 28

4.3.29 Young Leaders Video 29

Denk goed na met de dingen die je ziet en zoek eerst uit of het wel echt is

Be critical about the things you see and find out if it is real.

Partner	WAAG
Description	Participant create a video to share methods to counter disinformation in social media.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/29-CCLab-VoY-Video-WAAG-02.mp4

Table 34: Young Leaders Video 29

4.3.30 Young Leaders Video 30

Partner	WAAG
Description	Participants critically examine the use of social media apps, and how they can be used to spread disinformation.
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/15495042/files/30-CCLab-VoY-Video-WAAG-03.mp4

Table 35: Young Leaders Video 30

5 Next Steps

The viewership and audience reach of the *Young Leaders Video Campaign* is expected to continue to grow, as more videos are promoted across channels and are integrated into upcoming communication actions such as the Critical ChangeLab stories which focus more on the educational and research outcomes of the individual labs. These communication actions will be reported at the next milestone of continuous reporting of the Participant Portal.

Beyond online distribution, the videos will be featured at events such as the Ars Electronica Festival and will be integrated in upcoming campaigns to support the communication of the Critical ChangeLab's MOOC, educator materials, and policy briefs, extending their utility into educational and advocacy domains.

Despite delays caused by the staggered scheduling of PAR Cycle 3 and consent-related challenges, the majority of partners delivered their video content by Month 26 with additional videos are expected from two partners in the coming months as PAR Cycle 3 Labs are finalised.

6 Conclusion

The Young Leaders Video campaign stands as a testament to the Critical ChangeLab project's core principles: youth agency, creative expression, and participatory democracy. From its original conception as a component of youth mentoring, the campaign grew into a cross-consortium effort that gave young people a platform to express their views, experiences, and aspirations in their own voices and on their own terms.

Through the co-creation of short videos, young participants not only reflected on their learning within the Critical ChangeLabs but also contributed meaningfully to the project's broader public narrative. Their contributions have helped to reframe youth not as passive recipients of democratic education, but as active narrators and leaders in shaping democratic futures. The campaign has also demonstrated how flexible and decentralised coordination—anchored in shared values and supported by clear, adaptable tools—can yield cohesive, high-quality outputs across diverse contexts.

Looking forward, the campaign offers a sustainable model for participatory communication in youth-focused initiatives. The videos will continue to serve as learning tools, conversation starters, and policy advocacy material well beyond the project's duration, reinforcing Critical ChangeLab's lasting commitment to elevating youth voice in democratic education.

7 Annexes

Annex 1: Participant Consent Form Template

Annex 1: Participant Consent Form Template

As part of the Critical ChangeLab project, the Young Leaders video series seeks to provide young people across Europe with a platform for creating impactful videos that capture their voices, experiences and aspirations. Thank you for your participation and support in the "Young Leaders" video series – your voice matters, and we're excited to share it with the world!

Participant Information

- Name:
- Date of Birth:
- Age:
- School/Organization (if applicable):

Guardian Information

- Name:
- Relationship to Participant:
- Phone Number:
- Email Address:

Purpose of the series

The **Young Leaders video series** is part of the Critical ChangeLab project, aimed at amplifying the voices of young people on issues of social justice, equality, and civic engagement. Participants will create and appear in videos that may be shared on social media and other platforms associated with Critical ChangeLab, allowing their messages to reach a broad audience.

Consent to Participate

- **Participant's Agreement:** I, the undersigned participant, agree to take part in the "Young Leaders" video series. I understand that my participation may include recording videos where I express my views, opinions, and experiences related to involvement in the Critical ChangeLab project..
- **Guardian Consent** (for participants under 18 years old): I, the undersigned guardian of the participant, consent to my child's participation in the "Young Leaders" video series. I

understand that this includes their involvement in video production, which may be shared publicly.

Use of Video Content

By signing this consent form, I acknowledge and agree to the following:

Recording and Use: The video(s) created during this series will be recorded, edited, and potentially shared through Critical ChangeLab partners' social media channels (such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter) and other digital platforms.

Public Access: I understand that the videos may be publicly accessible and viewed by a global audience. This includes, but is not limited to, members of the general public, organizations, and media outlets.

Rights and Ownership: I grant Critical ChangeLab the right to use, reproduce, distribute, and display the videos for promotional, educational, and advocacy purposes. This consent extends to the use of the participant's name, voice, likeness, and any statements made in the videos.

Compensation: I understand that participation in this series is voluntary, and no monetary compensation will be provided for the creation or distribution of the videos.

Withdrawal: I am aware that participation is voluntary, and I may withdraw consent at any time by contacting a Critical ChangeLab project member. However, I understand that once the video is published, it may be difficult to remove all copies from public platforms.

Signatures

Participant signature & date:

Guardian signature & date:

Contact Information

For any questions or concerns regarding this consent form or the "Young Leaders" video series, please contact:

[Contact Name] [Insert Contact Email] [Insert Contact Phone Number]

